

JAVASCRIPTDA OPERATORLAR VA IFODALAR

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Anotatsiya: Ushbu tezis operatorlar va ifodalar mavzusini tushuntirishga qaratilgan. Bu erda operatorlar nima ekanligi, qanday turlari borligi, qanday tartibda ishlaydiganligi haqida ma'lumot beriladi. Shuningdek, ifodalar nima ekanligi, qanday tuzilishi kerakligi, qanday qiymat qaytaradiganligi haqida ma'lumot beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: operator, ifoda, operand, qiymat, tartib.

Operatorlar va ifodalar JavaScript dasturlash tilidagi muhim qavramlardan biridir. Bu tezisda JavaScriptda foydalaniladigan operatorlar va ifodalar haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Operatorlar:

Aritmetik operatorlar: + (qo'shish), - (ayirish), * (ko'paytirish), / (bo'lish), % (qoldiq olish) aritmetik amallar uchun ishlatiladi. Misol uchun:

```
var x = 10;
var y = 5;
var sum = x + y; // 15
var difference = x - y; // 5
var product = x * y; // 50
var quotient = x / y; // 2
var remainder = x % y; // 0
```

Taqqoslash operatorlari: > (katta), < (kichik), >= (katta yoki teng), <= (kichik yoki teng), == (tenglik), != (teng emas) qiymatlar taqqoslashi uchun ishlatiladi. Misol uchun:

```
var a = 5;
var b = 10;
var isGreater = a > b; // false
var isLess = a < b; // true
var isEqual = a == b; // false
var isNotEqual = a != b; // true
```

Mantiqiy operatorlar: && (va), || (yoki), ! (emas) mantiqiy amallar uchun ishlatiladi. Misol uchun:

```
var x = true;
var y = false;
var result1 = x && y; // false
var result2 = x || y; // true
var result3 = !x; // false
```

Tenglik operatorlari: === (qat'iylashtirish), !== (qat'iylashmaydi) qiymatlar va tur taqqoslashi uchun ishlatiladi. Misol uchun:

```
var a = 5;
var b = "5";
var isEqualStrict = a === b; // false
var isNotEqualStrict = a !== b; // true
```

Ifodalar:

Ifodalar dasturlashda shartlarni tekshirish, tanlash va dastur bajarish uchun ishlatiladi. Quyidagi ifoda turlari JavaScriptda foydalaniladi:

If-else ifodasi: Shartlarni tekshirish va undan kelib chiqqan natijalarni boshqa shartlar orqali yoki shart bajarilmaganida ishlatish uchun ishlatiladi. Misol uchun:

```
var age = 18;
if (age >= 18) {
  console.log("Siz ovoz berish haqida qatnashishingiz mumkin");
} else {
  console.log("Siz ovoz berish haqida qatnashib bo'lmaysiz");
}
```

Ternary ifodasi: qisqa shartli ifoda, bir shartni tekshirish va shart bajarilsa va bajarilmasligini aniqlash uchun ishlatiladi. Ternary ifodasi quyidagi ko'rinishda yoziladi:

shart ? ifoda1 : ifoda2

Agar shart rost bo'lsa, ifoda1 bajariladi; aks holda, ifoda2 bajariladi. Misol uchun:

```
var age = 18;
var message = (age >= 18) ? "Siz ovoz berish haqida qatnashishingiz mumkin" : "Siz ovoz berish haqida qatnashib bo'lmaysiz";
console.log(message);
```

Bu misolda, agar age 18 yoki undan katta bo'lsa, message o'zgaruvchisiga "Siz ovoz berish haqida qatnashishingiz mumkin" qiymati tayinlanadi; aks holda, "Siz ovoz berish haqida qatnashib bo'lmaysiz" qiymati tayinlanadi.

Switch ifodasi: Bir nechta qiymatlarni tekshirish uchun ishlatiladi. Shart qiymatlariga mos bo'lgan bloklar bajariladi. Misol uchun:

```
var day = "Dushanba";
switch (day) {
  case "Dushanba":
    console.log("Bugun ish kuni");
    break;
  case "Seshanba":
  case "Chorshanba":
  case "Payshanba":
  case "Juma":
    console.log("Hafta kuni");
    break;
  default:
    console.log("Hafta tashqarisi");
    break;
}
```

Agar day o'zgaruvchisi "Dushanba"ga teng bo'lsa, "Bugun ish kuni" chiqadi. Aks holda, "Hafta kuni" chiqadi. Agar day qiymati hech qaysi shartga mos kelmasa, "Hafta tashqarisi" chiqadi.

Ifodalar JavaScript dasturlashda shartlarni to'g'ri tekshirish, belgilangan amallarni bajarish va shart bo'lgan holatlarda dasturlarni yo'lga qo'yish imkonini beradi. Bu qavramlarni tushuntirish va o'rganish, dasturlashni amalga oshirishda asosiydir.

Xulosa

Operatorlar va ifodalar dasturlash tilining eng kichik va eng muhim elementlari bo'lib, ular ma'lumotlarni hisoblash va o'zgartirish uchun ishlatiladi. Operatorlar va ifodalarning turli turlari va xususiyatlari bor bo'lib, ularning to'g'ri ishlatilishi dasturlash jarayonini soddalashtiradi va kodni optimallashtiradi.

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